

ON SOME NEW TYPES OF SMALL CARNIVOROUS MAMMAL-LIKE
*REPTILES.

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(With Seven Text-Figures.)

In the earlier days of fossil hunting in South Africa the very large majority of specimens collected were moderately large. The first specimen collected by A. G. Bain in 1838 was a *Pareiasaurus*, and, with the exception of a few specimens of *Cistecephalus*, there is not in the large collection sent by him to the British Museum the remains of a single small mammal-like reptile. The large majority of our fossil hunters have been amateurs, and they also have picked up mainly large and moderate sized skulls.

The young Kitchings, who have done much collecting for Mr. S. H. Rubidge, have gathered more extensively than others and have hunted for small as systematically as for large. As a result there are in Mr. Rubidge's collection many skulls and skeletons of small animals which the senior author has from time to time described.

About two years ago Dr. Bernard Price very generously came forward to help in the work of fossil hunting, and the services of James and Ben Kitching were engaged, and for six months they were employed in hunting new fossil areas. As a result a magnificent collection has been made which includes many valuable and interesting new types. In the present paper we are describing a few new small carnivorous Therapsids.

Aelurodraco microps gen. et sp. nov. (Figs. 1 & 2).

This new genus is founded on a good skull which lacks the arches. It was discovered at Hoeksplaas, Murraysburg Dist. Though the type is allied to the already known pre-Cynodonts *Procynosuchus*, and three other genera *Leavachia*, *Galeophrys* and *Galecranium* which the senior author is describing in the *Trans. Roy. Soc. Ed.*, it differs in the dentition and a number of cranial characters.

In greatest length the skull measures from the snout to the occipital condyle 91 mm, and the width across the temporal arches has been about 68 mm.

* This paper was deliberately annexed by the Committee, who felt that its publication here should prove an interesting and justifiable departure from current practice.—Editor.

It is thus the smallest of the known pre-Cynodonts, and only about half the size of *Leavachia*.

As in the other known genera the parietals form a considerable median crest, but as the top is broken off it is impossible to say how high it has been, but probably not higher than shown in the figure. The pineal foramen is fairly developed, but smaller than in the allied known genera.

The postorbitals are well developed, and their posterior processes clasp the front of the parietals. The post-orbital arch appears to pass almost directly outwards, but only the outer and inner bases are preserved.

The frontals are relatively small, and in the specimen the left one is considerably larger than the right. Each is bordered by the nasal, the prefrontal, the postorbital and the parietal, but the suture between the frontal and the

FIG. 1. Side view of skull of *Aelurodraco microps* B. & R.—Natural size.

parietal cannot be made out. The prefrontal is well developed on each side, and each forms most of the upper border of the orbit.

The nasal is very large, and as in all Cynodonts the posterior portion is much broader than the anterior. Posteriorly each nasal articulates with the frontal, the prefrontal and the lacrimal. By the side of the nasal can be seen on the left side much of the septomaxilla, but it is not well preserved in front. The lacrimal forms most of the front of the orbit.

The premaxilla is fairly well developed, but it is much overlapped by the maxilla. In front of the large canine there are seven small pointed teeth, of which we believe the anterior six to be incisors, and the posterior one to be a small anterior canine. The six incisors together measure 12.5 mm.

The maxilla is of the usual Cynodont type. Along its lower border, and about 3 to 4 mm from the alveolar margin are a number of small foramina probably for branches of the Vth nerve. These seem to suggest that the animal may have had a flexible and probably muscular lip. The main canine is only

moderately large. Its base has an antero-posterior length of 5.2 mm. A few low ridges run down the crown, but there seem to be no serrations developed. The crown has a height (length) of something over 10mm. In front of the main canine and 2 mm from it is a small anterior canine of about similar size to the incisors.

Behind the canine are 8 postcanine or molar teeth. These measure together 21mm. Though nearly all the teeth are present the crowns are broken. Most of the crowns appear to be flattened and rather blunt points. One certainly

FIG. 2. Upper view of skull *Aeluradraco microps*
B. & R.—Natural size.

shows evidence of small cusps, and probably all the posterior ones had flattened crowns with 2 small and one larger cusp.

In the temporal fossa the parietal forms a large side well to the brain as in Cynodonts, and near the lower border of the parietal is a well marked groove for the large venous sinus. Below the parietal is a relatively small but broad alisphenoid, and a small prootic. The condition is closely similar to that in the better known *Procynosuchus delaharpeae* (Ann.Tr.Mus. XIX pt.2, 1938,

p.282). It is interesting to note that even the peculiar posterior process of the frontal which passes beneath the parietal is here repeated.

The occiput has only the median two-thirds satisfactorily preserved. It is essentially similar to that of *Leavachia* where the whole occiput is fully known.

No attempt has been made to clean out the palate as the mandibles are present and the right one is crushed over on the palate. But the palate is fully known in the allied *Procynosuchus*. The stapes in the new form has a large foramen as in *Procynosuchus*.

Both the dentaries are fairly well preserved, and most of the posterior part of the left mandible and a considerable part of the surangular of the right jaw.

The dentaries are rather robust. As the jaws are in position the teeth cannot be seen, except a few of the incisors. The coronoid process is but slightly developed, and only rises a little above the top of the surangular.

The outer plate of the angular is imperfect, but has probably been as restored in the drawing. The inner and back part of the angular which articulates with the surangular and articular is well preserved, and is as shown in the figure. The surangular forms the upper part of the posterior quarter of the jaw. It is quite strongly developed and appears to clasp the articular.

Having the posterior part of the jaw well preserved and in position we can restore the suspensorium with confidence; and we find it must agree closely with that in *Leavachia*. In *Leavachia* where the parts are perfectly preserved the squamosal is well developed, and there is a large quadratojugal.

It has been suggested by various authors that the outer plate of the angular clasped an anterior development of the tympanic cavity. The suggestion was, we believe, first made by R. W. Palmer in 1913, and it looks as if the curved lower part of the tympanic bone of mammals might be the homologue of the somewhat similar outer part of the angular in Cynodonts. The senior author always opposed this view. And if we look at the condition in this fossil skull it appears to be most improbable. The stapes and quadrate are practically on the occiput, and the tympanic membrane must have been attached to the quadrate and opisthotic. How a development could have reached the outside of the jaw and come to fit in between the two plates of the angular we cannot see. The senior author has suggested that space between the two plates of the angular was occupied by the submaxillary gland.

This new pre-Cynodont we propose to call *Aelurodraco microps*. Though in many characters it resembles forms already known it differs considerably in proportion and it has a different dental formula.

Procynosuchus, the first described form of the group, has 2 canines and 10 molars. In a paper being published by the Royal Society of Edinburgh the senior author has described three new genera. The largest of these has been called *Leavachia*. It has three canines and eight molars. Then there is a small

genus *Galeophrys* with 3 canines and 9 molars, and a second small genus *Galecranium* with 3 canines and 11 molars.

For convenience the genera may be arranged thus :—

<i>Procynosuchus</i>	i6	c2	m10
<i>Aelurodraco</i>	i6	c2	m8
<i>Leavachia</i>	i6	c3	m8
<i>Galeophrys</i>	i6	c3	m9
<i>Galecranium</i>	i6	c3	m11.

All the known forms of the group belong to the *Cistecephalus* zone.

Whaitsia pricei sp. nov. (Figs. 3 & 4).

The genus *Whaitsia* was described by S. H. Haughton in 1918. The type skull *Whaitsia platyceps* had been found by the Rev. J. A. Waits at Zuurpoort, and sent to the Capetown Museum. The skull is fairly complete, but has lost both temporal arches. Haughton figures the upper surface and the palate

FIG. 3. Side view of skull of *Whaitsia pricei* B. & R.— $\frac{2}{3}$ natural size.

and some details of the front of the snout. In 1932, Broom figured the type skull, restoring it from a second specimen, and he gave a figure of the lower jaw, with many sections showing the structure of the mandible.

Since then many other skulls have been found some of which possibly belong to other species, and in 1930 Broom described a new species *Whaitsia major*.

Besides these two species there are a number of others belonging to allied genera. *Moschorhynchus latirostris* was described in 1936. It differs from *Whaitsia* in having 4 incisors. *Notosollasia luckhoffi* was also described in 1936. It has 5 incisors, but differs from *Whaitsia* in the structure of the palate.

Among the specimens recently collected by the Kitchings for the Bernard Price Foundation is a well preserved small skull about half the size of that of *Whaitsia platyceps*. It differs in so many details of structure that we consider

that it cannot be a young specimen of *W. platyceps*, and consider it to be the type of a distinct species.

The specimen was found at Hoeksplaas, Murraysburg Dist. The skull is practically complete, but is considerably crushed, and the front of the nose and the postparietal region have been weathered. The mandibles are nearly perfectly preserved, but the left one is crushed on to the palate so that the palate cannot be examined.

When complete the skull measured about 138mm., and the greatest width is about 100 mm. The whole skull is remarkably flat, and the snout is considerably broader than deep. The orbits are larger than in the previously known species.

FIG. 4. Skull of *Waitsia pricei* B. & R.— $\frac{1}{2}$ natural size.

The antero-posterior diameter of the orbits is about 25mm. The interorbital width is 31mm and the intertemporal about 14mm. The temporal fossae are large and wide.

There is no clear evidence of a pineal foramen. In the specimen the parietals are broken in the middle line at a point indicated in the figure. There may be a pineal foramen here. If so, it is certainly small. The parietals are a little

wider than in the previously described species, and a little differently shaped. The postorbitals have rather broad posterior plates which lie on the parietals, and somewhat slender outer processes which form much of the postorbital arches. There are no postfrontals.

Each frontal is a little larger than broad, and each forms a small part of the orbital margin. Owing to the interorbital region being narrower and to the prefrontal encroaching more on them the frontals are differently shaped from those of *W. platyceps*.

The prefrontals are relatively larger than in *W. platyceps* and the lacrimals are also larger.

The nasals are broader than in the previously known species, especially in the plane of the front of the prefrontals, and the whole snout is broader and flatter.

The premaxillaries are not well preserved. Each has 5 incisors which together measure about 11mm. The 5th incisor is smaller than the others. Between the 5th incisor and the canine is a diastema of about 5 mm. but owing to crushing the measurement is not certain. Neither septomaxillary is well preserved.

The maxillaries have each one canine which at its base measures antero-posteriorly about 10 mm. There is no trace of any molar teeth. On the side of the maxilla there is a low boss or tumescence near where the upper end of the canine root probably lies.

The jugal is well developed, and it is shaped much as in the other species, but as the temporal arch is here feebler the posterior process is thinner.

The squamosal, as in the other species, is well developed. It probably covers a small quadratojugal and a larger quadrate, but owing to crushing these bones cannot be satisfactorily seen.

Below the parietal on the inner side of the temporal fossa there is a large alisphenoid, but owing to crushing a good drawing of it cannot be made. Owing to the parietal being much smaller than in Cynodonts the alisphenoid is relatively considerably larger.

The occiput owing to crushing is not very satisfactorily preserved. It is interesting from the relatively large size of the tabulars.

The palate is completely hidden by the left lower jaw, and by a mass of crushed vertebrae. As the front of the palate is completely known in the allied *Notosollasia*, and nearly the whole of the palate in *Moschorhynchus* it seems unnecessary to clean out the palate of this specimen as it would mean the removal and probably the damaging considerably of the jaws. In the two previously known species of *Whatisia* though the palate is fairly well known the sutures are difficult to determine, especially in the front of the palate.

The outer sides of both jaws are fairly well preserved, and are as shown in the figure. The dentary is rather strongly developed and there is a good coronoid

process. There are no molar teeth, and the number of incisors cannot be determined.

The angular has a well developed outer plate which is as shown in the figure.

We have much pleasure in naming this new species after Dr. Bernard Price.

Aneugomphius ictidoceps gen. et sp. nov. (Figs. 5 B, C ; 6 B & 7 A)

The type of this interesting new genus and species was found by the Kitchings at Hoekplaas, Murraysburg Dist. It is a nearly perfect skull, defective only in that the frontal and nasal regions have been somewhat broken and crushed down. Though the skull is that of an immature animal it is by far the smallest member of the interesting group of late Therocephalians, which like the best known genus *Whaitsia* have no molar teeth.

In greatest length the skull measures 68mm and the greatest width is 49mm. The interorbital measurement is 15 mm and the intertemporal 8 mm.

FIG. 5. (A) Upper view of skull of *Ictidodraaco longiceps* B. & R.
 (B) Upper view of skull of *Aneugomphius ictidoceps* B. & R.
 (C) Occiput of *Aneugomphius ictidoceps* B. & R.
 (All natural size.)

The back part of the parietals is perfect but the front half is broken and crushed down. It is impossible to say whether there is a pineal foramen. If one is present it must be quite small, and in the position shown in the figure. The postorbitals clasp the sides of the front of the parietals. They form feeble postorbital arches. There are no postfrontals.

Each frontal is about twice as long as broad, and each forms a small part of the orbital margin. The prefrontals are well developed, and the lacrimals about half as large.

The nasals are a little broader behind than in front. The septomaxilla is of the usual Therocephalian type.

The premaxillae are well preserved except for the ascending internasal process which is lost. Each has five slender incisors. As preserved the 1st is longest, and the 2nd shorter and the 3rd still smaller. The 4th is about as large as the 2nd and the 5th the smallest of the series. Each is a very slender rounded pointed tooth. Together they measure 5.8 mm. Probably the 3rd and 5th are young teeth.

The maxilla in the region of the canine is fairly deep. Posteriorly a long process passes below the jugal to beyond the plane passing through the middle of the orbit. In both maxillae there are in the specimen two canines. The posterior one is only about half the size of the other. Manifestly the posterior one is an earlier canine which is being replaced by the larger anterior. There are no molars or premolars, but the alveolar border of the bone is rough and broadened, suggesting that possibly there may have been some molars at an earlier stage of development. Years ago the senior author described an allied form *Lycideops longiceps*, which has 8 very small molars. These molars appear to be too feeble to be of any functional use, and they are probably shed before the animal is adult.

The jugal bone is small and not unlike that in *Whaitsia*, but far more slender. The squamosal is also essentially similar to that in *Whaitsia*, but much more feebly developed. On the lower border of the posterior and outer side of the squamosal is a little notch in which lies a small quadratojugal bone.

Below the parietal on the inner wall of the temporal fossa is a quite well developed alisphenoid.

The occiput is well preserved. The interparietal is small and entirely on the occiput. In many Therocephalians and in the occiput of *Notaelurops paucidens* which is allied to this new form, the parietals form a large part of the occiput above the interparietal. In this new form the parietals form just the upper border of the occiput. The tabulars are almost as deep as broad, which is in contrast to the condition of *Whaitsia* where they are very broad. They form the upper border of the lateral occipital foramen.

The supra-occipital is a little larger than the interparietal. The exoccipitals are small. Below the lateral foramen the opisthotic has a moderately developed

lateral process which articulates with the squamosal. The back part of the squamosal supports the small quadratojugal and the larger but small quadrate. There is a short but not slender stapes. In the allied *Notaelurops* the stapes is long and slender.

The whole occiput agrees essentially with that of *Notaelurops* differing only in the different relative proportions of the bones. In the large but allied *Hyenosaurus platyceps* the differences are much greater.

Though the palate cannot be completely cleaned owing to the mandibles being in position a good deal of the structure can be seen. There does not appear to be a foramen in the stapes.

The pterygoids are well developed. Each has an anterior process which meets the prevomer and articulates with the palatine. The transverse process descends to near the lower border of the jaw, and much of its outer side is supported by the transpalatine which is small. If there is any suborbital opening between the transpalatine, the palatine and the pterygoid it must be quite small. Between the two pterygoids in the plane of the transverse processes there is a small median vacuity. And immediately outside this vacuity the pterygoid forms a marked little process which carries two small rounded teeth. Posteriorly the pterygoid articulates with the vomer (parasphenoid of most authors).

The front of the palate is probably as we have restored it. The whole structure is known except what is shown in dotted line. The maxillae certainly approach each other closely, and there is probably a membranous secondary palate. The back part of what is probably the beginning of a rudimentary secondary palate is seen in the specimen.

The outer side of the left mandible has been cleaned, and the bones are as shown in the figure. The dentary is long and though not deep moderately thick. It seems probable that in all this family mastication was largely performed by the edentulous dentary working against the toothless maxilla and palatine.

The angular has a large outer plate such as is shown in the figure. The articulation is broad and appears to be with both the quadratojugal and the quadrate.

We propose to call this interesting new type *Aneugomphius icidoceps*.

It is very remarkable that in the *Cistecephalus* zone a whole group of *Terocephalians* should be found all characterised by having no postcanine teeth, and perhaps just as remarkable that we should find some *Gorgonopsians* of the same period losing their molars.

The very large *Gorgonopsians*, *Smilesaurus* and *Rubidgea*, have only a couple of small molars left. The large *Pardocephalus* has only one molar; while the genus *Clelandia* has no molars left.

Among the *Terocephalians* we find the same thing happening. In *Moschorhinus* the molars are degenerating. At most only four small ones are

left, and they apparently drop out in adult or later life as we find specimens with no molars left.

In the whole group of genera Hyenosaurus, Whaitsia, Moschorhynchus, Notosollasia, Alopecopsis, Notaelurops and Aneugomphius we find no trace of molars. And the very aberrant Euchambersia possibly belongs to the same group. It also has lost all molars.

Probably in Cistecephalus times some change in the fauna resulted in the lessened need for molar teeth. Could it perhaps be the evolution of Cistecephalus itself, and the great abundance of this small Anomodont during much of this period?

Ictidodraco longiceps gen. et. sp. nov. (Figs. 5A & 6A).

The type of this very interesting new form of Therocephalian is a skull with part of the skeleton found by the Kitchings at Ringsfontein, Murraysburg Dist.

The skull, which is very unlike any one previously known, is long and narrow, and fortunately it is nearly perfect. In greatest length it measures 88mm, and the greatest width is probably about 42mm. From the front of the orbit to the front of the snout the measurement is 46 mm, so that the orbit is entirely in the posterior half of the skull. The orbit has an anteroposterior measurement of about 18 mm. The interorbital width is 14 mm and the intertemporal 9 mm.

The parietals are well developed. There is a small pineal foramen between them. The postorbitals are small. They clasp the anterior parts of the parietals and each has a fairly long articulation with the frontal. They form a feeble but complete postorbital arch.

The frontals are each a little more than twice as long as broad. Each forms a considerable part of the orbital margin. The prefrontals are moderately large and each stands out a little from the general level of the adjoining bones. The lacrimals are also fairly large.

The nasals are also very long and narrow. Each is a little broader behind than in front. The septomaxillary is of the usual Therocephalian type.

The premaxillaries are fairly well preserved though the internasal process is lost. Each bone carries six long pointed rounded incisors. Together they measure 9.8 mm.

The maxilla is a long rather flat bone. It carries one well developed canine and 10 postcanine or molar teeth. There is no small canine in front of the large canine and the distance between it and the 6th incisor is 4 mm. The canine has an anteroposterior measurement at its base of 3.5 mm. The canine is rounded in section and so far as preserved it does not show any serrations. Between the canine and the 1st molar is a diastema of about 4mm. The 10 molars

together measure 16.5 mm. All the molars are small pointed teeth, and there appear to be no serration on any.

In front of the canine there are three foramina on the maxilla probably for branches of the Vth nerve. Most of the maxillary bone is extremely thin—about as thin as note paper, and the bone of much of the nasal and prefrontal is just as thin. A similar character is found in the bones of the snout of the very aberrant Therocephalian *Rubidgina angusticeps*, and though this new type we are describing is not closely allied to *Rubidgina* it is interesting to find this character in a form which is much nearer to typical Therocephalians.

FIG. 6. (A) Side view of skull of *Ictidodraco longiceps* B. & R.
 (B) Side view of skull of *Aneugomphius ictidoceps* B. & R.
 (C) Side view of skull of *Tetracynodon tenuis* B. & R.
 (All natural size.)

The jugal bone is very feebly developed but of the usual Therocephalian type. It forms much of the temporal arch. The squamosal forms much of the back and outer wall of the temporal fossa. It is fairly deep but does not, as in *Rubidgea*, form a marked descending suspensorium. There is, however, a notch on the outer lower border of the bone and in this is seen a small quadra-tojugal, which forms part of the articulation for the jaw.

Owing to crushing the occiput cannot be satisfactorily seen, but it appears to be of the usual Therocephalian type.

The palate cannot be seen owing to the jaws being in position and to crushing. In a transverse fracture part of the alisphenoid can be examined. It resembles more the usual Therocephalian type than that seen in *Whaitsia*.

The mandibles of both sides are satisfactorily displayed. The dentary is long and slender, and the coronoid process is only feebly developed, the top of it only rising very slightly above the surangular. The angular has a very large flattened thin outer plate. It is larger, relatively, than in any other known Therocephalian. This plate is supported by a well developed stellate arrangement of thickened bony ridges. The other bones of the jaw so far as can be seen are of the usual type.

Behind the skull are 7 cervical vertebrae and there are also to be seen a number of displaced dorsal vertebrae. In the piece of matrix behind the skull lie portions of one front limb and a number of other bones; but as the matrix is hard and the bones confusedly huddled together and as more of the skeleton may be picked up at the site where the specimen was obtained, it seems better that any discussion of the post-cranial bones should be deferred for the present.

We propose calling this interesting new Therocephalian *Ictidodraco longiceps*. It is difficult to state its affinities as it is not closely allied to any previously described form. It differs from Scaloposaurids in having the postorbital arch complete and in having only one canine. The top of the skull is not unlike that of *Ictidosuchoides longiceps*, but this has two small canines in front of the main one. The previously described form that it perhaps comes nearest to is *Ictidognathus parvidens* though this differs in having a small canine in front of the main one. Like the present form it has 6 incisors, but it has only 9 molars.

Tetracynodon tenuis gen. et sp. nov. (Fig 6C & 7B).

The skull which forms the type of this new genus and species belongs to Mr. Rubidge's collection. I believe it was collected by one of the Kitchings in the New Bethesda area and thus to belong to some parts of the Cistecephalus zone.

The skull is that of a small late Therocephalian of the Scaloposaurus group. It is rather badly weathered on the left side, but the right side is satisfactorily preserved.

In greatest length the skull measures about 66.5 mm. and the greatest width is about 32 mm. The orbital measurement is 11 mm, and the intertemporal 9 mm.

The parietals are fairly broad and there is no pineal foramen. There is a well developed postorbital which does not form a complete postorbital arch. There is no postfrontal.

The frontals are about twice as long as broad. Each forms much of the upper orbital margin. The prefrontal is relatively small. The lacrimal is longer than the prefrontal, but not so wide. The nasal is long and moderately broad.

FIG. 7. (A) Palatal view of skull of *Aneugomphius ictidoceps* B. & R. As the lower jaw was in position, the exact nature of the anterior part of the palate is unknown, but from the indication in the parts that can be seen, it is probably as drawn.

(B) Upper view of skull of *Tetracynodon tenuis* B. & R.

(Both natural size.)

If the top of the skull be compared with that of *Scaloposaurus constrictus* Owen, it will be seen that there is essential agreement, though a good deal of difference in the shapes of the bones, and there can be little doubt that the two forms belong to the same family and to fairly closely related genera. It is when we examine the dentition that we find a very marked difference.

The premaxillae are remarkably long, and there are preserved 6 incisors, but there must be two—possibly three—in front of the first incisor preserved on the right side. On the left side the anterior teeth are less satisfactorily

preserved, but there appear to be 8 incisors, and we think the evidence is in favour of there being only 8. Together they measure 8.2 mm.

The maxilla is a long rather slender bone. It carries one main canine with 3 small canines in front of it. Together the 4 canines measure 5.6 mm. Though the main canine is three or four times as large as the incisors, the other canines and the molars, it is still a remarkably small canine for a Therocephalian. As the snout has been broken across just behind the main canine and the fracture badly weathered, it is difficult to say where the small molar teeth begin. There is clearly the remains of a deciduous canine behind the functional one, and there does not appear to be any molar till we come to a small one which is 4 mm behind the functional canine. Behind this small molar are 8 and a gap where apparently there was another. We can thus assume as probable that there were 10 very small molars. These together measure 10.8 mm. We thus believe the upper dental formula to be $i8\ c4\ m10$. In *Scaloposaurus* it is apparently $i6\ c3\ m9$.

The jugal is very slender, and the squamosal though much wider is also slender. On the right side the squamosal is satisfactorily preserved, and the structure is shown in the figures given. On the lower outer border there is a notch in which is seen a small quadratojugal. The thin upper plate of the squamosal is seen resting on the parietal.

The articular region is not preserved. The quadrate must, however, be very small.

Much of the occiput of the right side is preserved though a little crushed. The interparietal is broad and narrow and nearly reaches the top of the occiput. The tabular is also broad and narrow.

Parts of the palate have been displayed, but the bones are a little crushed and displaced. So far as can be seen the palate agrees essentially with that of *Scaloposaurus*.

The lower jaw is essentially similar to that of *Scaloposaurus*. The dentary is very long and only slightly curved. In front there are certainly at least 6 incisors. But no other teeth can be seen owing to the jaws being in position and the mouth nearly closed. The angular is also very like that of *Scaloposaurus*. The posterior bones are not satisfactorily seen.

This little type is clearly closely related to *Scaloposaurus*, and it differs mainly in having many more incisors. It agrees with it in having no frontal foramen.

In 1940 the senior author described (*Ann. Trans. Mus.* XX, 2) two related forms with which comparison must be made. The first is a little type only slightly larger than the one being described which was named *Scaloposuchus rubidgei*. It is also an ally of *Scaloposaurus*, but it differs in having more incisors and canines and in having a well developed pineal foramen.

Scaloposuchus has apparently 8 upper incisors and it has 3 very small canines in front of the main canine, and it appears to have 12 molars. In the lower jaw there are 6 incisors, 1 canine and 15 molars.

The other allied form described in 1940 was called *Octocynodon elegans*. It is a very much larger animal than the very small one being described, and unfortunately it is only known by the anterior half of the skull. It has 3 rather well developed canines in front of the main upper canine and it has 6 incisors. The generic name *Octocynodon* is unfortunately pre-occupied (Fowler 1904) and we propose for it *Polycynodon*.

The new little animal we propose to call *Tetrocynodon tenuis*; and the following key will show how it differs from some allied forms.

	<i>Incisors</i>	<i>Canines</i>	<i>Molars</i>	<i>Pineal</i>
<i>Scaloposaurus constrictus</i> Owen	6	3	9	<i>Absent</i>
<i>Scalopocephalus watsonianus</i> v. Huene	6	2	?	?
<i>Choerosaurus dejageri</i> Haughton	6	3	12	<i>Present</i>
<i>Scaloposuchus rubidgei</i> Broom	8	4	12	<i>Present</i>
<i>Polycynodon elegans</i> (Broom)	6	4	9	?
<i>Ictidosuchoides intermedius</i> Broom	6	3	8	<i>Large</i>
<i>Tetrocynodon tenuis</i> B. and R.	8	4	10 ⁺	<i>Absent</i>